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POLICY BRIEF

THE AMAZON SUMMIT: AN EMERGING DIALOGUE

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Why is it still necessary to discuss the Amazon? The Amazon Summit, which aimed to establish new measures for the preservation of the Amazon biome, was hosted in Belém, Pará, Brazil, on August 8th and 9th, 2023, and brought together representatives and leaders from countries that are members of the Amazon Cooperation Treaty Organization (ACTO). The declaration signed during the summit committed to new measures but did not include a common goal of zero deforestation. The dialogue surrounding the Amazon is one of the most crucial topics of our time because it is the most abundant biome among ACTO member countries, the largest tropical forest on the planet, and it directly influences the climate of South America. Let's first explore the benefits this biome provides to member countries of the bloc.

The Amazon is the most abundant biome among ACTO member countries. Eight member countries have a significant portion of the Amazon biome within their territories, including Brazil, Bolivia, Colombia, Ecuador, Guyana, Peru, Suriname, and Venezuela. These countries experience direct influences in various economic, political, and socio-environmental aspects. Brazil, in particular, holds over 60% of the biome. The region is home to approximately 40 million inhabitants, including traditional communities from these countries, and it harbors rich ethnic and cultural diversity. Now that we have discussed the Amazon biome in ACTO member countries let us examine the biodiversity of this magnificent tropical forest.

The Amazon rainforest is considered the largest tropical forest in the world, both in terms of size and resources. Its immense biological diversity provides crucial services to the regional ecosystem and its survival. It boasts the largest river basin globally, accounting for 20% of the planet's freshwater. Its natural resources include valuable timber, rubber, and plants with great potential to produce medicines, food, aromas, spices, dyes, and fibers. Additionally, the forest is home to 85% of South

America's fish species, over 400 species of amphibians, 1,300 bird species, and 400 mammal species. Lastly, we will examine the Amazon's influence on the climate of South American countries.

The third reason why discussing the Amazon is essential lies in its impact on the climate of South America. The forest's evapotranspiration system involves plant transpiration, which is responsible for around 50% of the Amazon's rainfall. According to the National Institute for Space Research (INPE), illegal practices prolong the dry seasons and increase temperatures in deforested areas, impacting the climate of neighboring preserved regions. This occurs because increased deforestation decreases water vapor emission into the atmosphere, reducing local and distant rainfall. After discussing the Amazon biome's influence on the climate of South America, we will present our final considerations.

In summary, the discussion surrounding the Amazon represents one of the most crucial topics of our time, deserving full consideration from society. The abundance of the Amazon biome is evident in ACTO member countries, where the tropical forest is recognized as the largest on the planet, with its undeniable direct influence on the climate of South America. We recommend that policymakers continue to engage with civil society to find alternatives to the challenges and opportunities posed by climate change. This is necessary for formulating a new sustainable development strategy for the Amazon based on the bioeconomy, providing a fresh perspective on the biome. In this perspective, the forest will be valued intact, turning ACTO into a geopolitical bloc of reference for socio-environmental issues.

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